

ANALYSIS OF PROFITABILITY OF PLANTAIN PROCESSING ENTERPRISES IN IJEBU NORTH LGA, OGUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to analyse the profitability of plantain processing enterprises in Ijebu North LGA, Ogun State. Multistage sampling procedure was used to select the study participants. To achieve the objectives, 120 plantain processing enterprises were interviewed with the use of well-structured questionnaire. The distribution of the households' socioeconomic characteristics revealed that a greater percentage of the respondents were male (71%) while the other percentage (29%) were female. Majority of the respondents were less than 50 years old. The mean age of household heads was 36 years. The majority of the respondents attested that roasted plantain was the most available product in the area, followed by flour and then chips. The result of the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) further reiterated the profitability of plantain processing in the area. The BCR value of 1.46 implies that for every one naira expended on processed plantain ₦1.46k is realized. The study concluded that the prospects of plantain processing are high. It is therefore a good business opportunity for creating employment for many Nigerians to become actors in the plantain value chain (as inputs dealers, farmers, marketers, transporters, and processors). The study therefore recommends that the Government could help processors expand their operations and invest in better equipment and infrastructure.

Keywords: Profitability, Gross margin, Profit and Enterprise

1. INTRODUCTION

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) is a large herbaceous plant cultivated in humid forests and mid latitude zones of sub-Saharan Africa, with its origins believed to trace back to Southeast Asia. Notably, sub-Saharan Africa boasts a remarkable diversity of plantain varieties (Akintade *et al.*, 2016). Plantains serve as valuable sources of starch and energy (Dankyi *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, plantain cultivation offers a viable income stream for small-scale farmers in the region. Smallholders predominantly engage in plantain farming, contributing significantly to food security and income generation for millions of impoverished rural communities worldwide, particularly in Africa and Latin America (Babatunde, 2010). Leading plantain producers include Uganda, Colombia, Ghana, Rwanda, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Nigeria, with an average yield of 15.7 tons per hectare (FAOSTAT, 2017).

Plantain is a significant staple food in many parts of Africa, including Nigeria. It is a versatile crop that can be processed into various products such as plantain chips, flour, and baby food. The plantain processing industry offers immense potential for entrepreneurship and economic development, particularly in rural areas. Plantain processing enterprises are becoming increasingly popular, providing employment opportunities and contributing to the local economy. Processing plantains not only adds value to the raw product but also extends its shelf life, thereby reducing post-harvest losses. According to Oke *et al.*, (2019), the processing of plantains into chips, flour, and other products can significantly enhance the income of rural households and reduce post-harvest losses. This industry can significantly impact the socioeconomic status of individuals and the community at large by generating income, creating jobs, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

Plantain is grown in 52 countries with World production at 33million metric tonnes (FAO, 2006). Eight African countries are named among the top ten World producers of plantain. Nigeria's production output was 2.103million metric tonnes in 2004 (FAO 2006; FAOSTAT, 2007). With the recent interest in the establishment of plantain farms, as evident by the increase in cultivation/harvested areas, the Nigeria's productivity will be trippled in the next few years. It is believed that the country will for a long time be one of the top producers of plantain around the world (Akinyemi and Mankinde, 2010).

Despite the significant growth of the plantain industry in Nigeria since the early 1960s, the country remains a net importer of plantain. This is primarily attributed to the domestic consumption of plantain far exceeding its production for export (Akintade *et al.*, 2016; Akinyemi, Aiyelaagbe, & Akyeampong, 2010). Plantain processing enterprises face unique challenges and opportunities. The region is known for its rich agricultural heritage, and plantains are one of the main crops cultivated. The local government has been encouraging agricultural processing as a means to boost the local economy and provide employment opportunities for the youth.

Previous research has consistently highlighted several constraints faced by the plantain sub sector in Nigeria, including high post-harvest losses, diseases, poor pricing, inadequate infrastructure, and transportation challenges (Ekunwe *et al.*, 2010). As with other crops, plantains are perishable, requiring careful handling and preservation. Fresh bananas and plantains have a limited shelf life, and rough handling, improper storage, and poor transportation can lead to post-production losses of 30-40% (Cauthen *et al.*, 2013). Due to its highly perishable nature, there is a prevailing need to convert raw plantain into variety of products in bid to reduce wastage and improve plantain output. Also, there is limited access to reliable data regarding the costs associated with plantain processing and distribution. This information gap impedes entrepreneurs from accurately assessing their operational expenses and potential profit margins. Lastly, the variability in market demand and pricing presents a significant hurdle for plantain processors. Fluctuations in consumer preferences, seasonality, and external factors such as weather conditions can significantly impact sales and revenue streams, making it difficult for enterprises to maintain consistent profitability. Based on the foregoing, the broad objective of the study was to analyse the profitability of plantain processing enterprises in Ijebu North, LGA Ogun State. Specific objectives were to;

1. Identify the main processed plantain products available in the study area.
2. Determine the profitability of plantain processors in the study area.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical review

Plantain is a basic food product contributing to the food security of millions of people in the developing world and constitutes a source of employment and income generation for the rural populace (Nkendah and Nzouessin, 2006). Plantain is grown in 52 countries with World

production at 33million metric tonnes (FAO, 2006). Eight African countries are named among the top ten World producers of plantain. Nigeria's production output was 2.103million metric tonnes in 2004 (FAO 2006; FAOSTAT, 2007). With the recent interest in the establishment of plantain farms, as evident by the increase in cultivation/harvested areas, the Nigeria's productivity will be trippled in the next few years. It is believed that the country will for a long time be one of the top producers of plantain around the world (Akinyemi and Mankinde, 2010). Plantain marketing involves the movement of plantain produce from the farms to the markets and this important activity is usually undertaken by middlemen who buy from farmers or traders and assemble the plantain bunches from the villages where they are produced. This is because productions which are mostly on small scales are also in fragments. Just like other agricultural commodities, plantain marketing is faced with the challenge of bulkiness, high transportation costs seasonality and rapid ease of perishability due to its short shelf life. The perishability nature of plantain makes its value addition and processing a vital link in the marketing process. Plantain has found a number of uses ranging from fried chips to plantain flour into which the pulp can be processed to secure it from deterioration and wastage. According to Adetunji and Adesiyani (2008), past efforts on plantain development was focussed on increased production technology without a corresponding increase in its marketing. Mellor (1992) drew attention to this situation when he noted that issues of marketing had been totally neglected in the literature of economic development of plantain and the obvious wastage the situation could cause if not addressed. Njoku and Nweke (1996) later in their writing supported the foregoing and came up with the view that the marketing condition of plantain changed because the aspect of marketing was neglected. Frison and Sharook (1998) stressed the importance of integrating the expression of marketing function with the expression of production. Akalumbe (1994) observed that marketing and post-harvest handling system of plantain in the Southern Nigeria was an important area requiring attention. This agreed with Njoku and Nweke (1995) who was of the view that good infrastructural facilities for improvement in plantain marketing system will further help plantain development programme. Dankyi et al, (2007) also in his report revealed that farmers are aware of the various production technologies, however low farm-gate pricing with traders determining prices has been a major hindrance to production and marketing. It is therefore obvious that increased production without corresponding well developed and efficient marketing system will amount to wastage of resources (Adetunji and Adesina, 2008). In view of the foregoing facts, it could be deduced that if marketing system of plantain is well understood, production could be expanded to ease the food security situation in Nigeria.

2.2 Empirical review

Akinbola and Aturamu (2021) empirically evaluates the profitability of small-scale plantain processing entrepreneurs in Osun State, Nigeria. Cross-sectional data were employed for the study, while a multi-stage sampling procedure was used to randomly select 120 respondents. Descriptive statistics, gross margin, and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) were used for the analysis of the data. The results showed the average values of gross margin (N23,592.50) and profit (N21,777.80) showed that the enterprise is profitable. The value of return on investment (1.73) implies that the processors are capable to realize N1.73k for every one naira invested. The results of OLS indicated that cost of bowl, plantain price, transport cost, and labour cost were the significant factors influencing profit accrued in the area. However, high cost of labour, lack of storage facility, and high cost of transportation were the most serious constraints faced by the processors in the area. Therefore, it can be recommended that a proactive policy that would address storage facility, good road networks and as well create enabling market environment should be put in place.

Ariyo *et al.*, (2013) carried out a study to analyze the profitability of plantain marketing and to examine the structure of plantain market in Kaduna Metropolis. Seventy five plantain

marketers were randomly selected from six purposively selected markets. Structural questionnaires were used to collect the data. Descriptive statistics, Cost and return analysis, Herfindahl index, Gross ratio, Operating ratio, Expense structure ratio, Return per capital invested, Benefit cost ratio were used to analyze the data. The study showed that majority (64%) of the plantain marketers were male. 65.3% are within the active age range of 31-60 years. Most respondents are married and educated having a household size of between 1-10 members. Herfindahl index of 0.03 revealed that plantain market tends towards perfect competition. The costs and return analysis showed that purchased cost, transportation, labour and storage cost constitute the variable cost and rent, tools and market charges forms the fixed cost. Furthermore, the finding showed that plantain marketing is profitable with the net return of 14,369 naira per month from the sales of 163 plantains bunches. Analysis of the profit revealed that plantain marketing is a profitable business. The constraint militating against marketing of plantain in the area were also identified to be high transportation cost, seasonal price fluctuation, rapid deterioration in quality/spoilage, inadequate capital, high initial cost of plantain, poor access road and high market charges. The study therefore recommends plantain marketers should come together to form plantain marketer's cooperative groups from which members could obtain loans at very low interest rates. Also problem of infrastructural facilities such as bad roads should be address by all tiers of governments.

3. Methodology

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ijebu North LGA in Ogun State, Nigeria which is located in the South West zone of the country with a total land area of 16,402.26 square kilometers, within a population of about 7 million people according to National Population Commission (N.P.C, 2016). The state is located in the rainforest vegetation belt of Nigeria within longitude 2 45' and 3° 55' E and latitudes 7 01 N and 7° 8' N in the tropics. It is bounded in the west by Benin Republic, in the south by Lagos state and Atlantic Ocean, in the east by Ondo State, and in the north by Oyo State. It covers a land area of 16,409.28 km², less than two percent (2%) of the country's landmass (Olaoye *et al.*, 2007). The state is warm throughout the year with a temperature of between 28 and 35°C. Humidity is between 85 and 95% (Oloruntoba and Adegbite, 2006). The state was divided into four agricultural extension zones namely: Abeokuta, Ilaro, Ijebu-Ode and Ikenne (OGADEC, 2005).

Sampling procedure and sample size

Dual-stage sampling procedure was employed for this study; Two-stage random sampling technique was used to select 120 plantain processors in Ijebu North LGA. The first stage was a random selection of six (6) wards in the local government (LGA). The second stage involved the random selection of twenty (20) respondents from each ward selected. This makes a total of 120 plantain processors used for the study.

Method of Data Collection.

Primary data for this study was collected from the plantain processors through the use of a well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule for the respondents that are illiterates. Data were collected on age, marital status, and household size including other household characteristics such as monthly income.

3.1 Model Specification Budgetary analysis technique

Gross margin analysis was used to analyse the profitability of Plantain processing enterprises in the study area and it is preferred because it allows the easy enterprise selection, determination of enterprise net income.

$$GM = TR - TVC \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$TR = P \times Q \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

GM = Gross Margin (₦)

TR = Total Revenue (₦) (price/kg × quantity sold)

TFC = Total Fixed Cost

P = Price of processed plantain products (₦)

Q = Quantity of Processed plantain products (₦)

ROI = Return on investment

$$ROI = TR/TVC \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

TR = Total Revenue accruable from the sales of plantain products

TVC = Total variable cost incurred in processing

TFC = Total Fixed Cost of Production

NI = GM - TFC

PI= Profitability Index

NI= Net Income

Previous studies on plantain show that plantain business or marketing is profitable Folyan and Bifani (2011). The profitability of plantain marketing which is objective five was determined using the Return per Capital Invested and Marketing Margin analysis. This is the difference between the retail or consumer price (CP) and the farm gate or supply price (SP). It is calculated mathematically as:

$$MM = \frac{\text{Selling price} - \text{Supply price}}{\text{Selling price}} * 100$$

Where: MM = Marketing Margin

CP = Consumer or Selling Price (N)

SP = Farm-gate or Supply Price (N)

VC = Variable Costs

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents.

The result in Table 1 reveals that the plantain processors were dominated by the male household with about 71%. This suggests that plantain processing in the study area was generally dominated by the male gender. This could be attributed to the tedious and strenuous nature of plantain processing. Most (33.3%) of the plantain processors fell in the age bracket of 31 - 40 years old with the mean age of 36 years old. This indicates that most of the processors were still in their youthful and economic age in the area. This is in support of (Aina *et al.*, 2012, Olaghere *et al.*, 2016) who reported that most of the people involved in marketing activities were young persons who are vibrant and energetic with a significant market influence. Results also show that 12.5% of the plantain processors in the study area were single while 71.67% were married, implying that the majority of the plantain processors was married. The mean household size was 4 persons with majority (68.3%) of the sampled plantain processors having a household size of 1 to 5 person. This is an indication that plantain processing enterprise is a

viable business that can sustain family livelihood but however implies that they will incur higher household expenditure that will reduce the quantum of income realizable from the enterprise. This is in line with the findings of Oluwasola and Ige (2015) who stated that household size is one of the factors of determining profitability of plantain processing enterprises. The education attainment of the respondents shows that 25% had tertiary education while 69.2% either have primary or secondary school certificates. This indicated that catfish farming was practiced as a business by people with varied levels of education with substantial proportion having post-secondary education. Moreover, about 69.17% of the respondents had processing experience of 1- 10 years, with an average mean of 7 years while 30.83% had an experience of above 10 years. This conforms with the finding of Onubuogu, (2012) that 29 experience in agribusiness enhances output performance. The mean household monthly income of the respondents was N96,417. This may have positive impact on the plantain processing enterprises in the study area. Majority (73.3%) do not have access to credit facilities. According to Olomola (2019), having access to loans can greatly improve the performance of small-scale farmers and is a key factor in determining agricultural production. A significant majority (67.5%) of processors did not receive visits from extension agents in the past year, indicating a gap in support services. Good extension services can improve processing and marketing methods and close the knowledge gap. Aina *et al.*, (2019) claim that the knowledge and practices of plantain processors are greatly enhanced by extension services, which raises profitability.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

Socioeconomic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex			
Male	85	70.83	
Female	35	29.17	
Age (years)			
≤ 30	32	26.67	36.17
31 – 40	40	33.33	
41 – 50	25	20.83	
51 – 60	12	10.00	
> 60	11	9.17	
Marital status			
Single	15	12.50	
Married	86	71.67	
Divorced	5	4.16	
Widow	14	11.67	
Household size			
1 – 5	82	68.33	3.75
6 – 10	38	31.67	
Educational level			
No formal	7	5.83	
Primary	42	35.00	
Secondary	41	34.17	
Tertiary	30	25.00	
Plantain processing experience			
1 – 10	83	69.17	7.16
11 – 20	27	22.50	
> 20	10	8.33	
Household Monthly Income			

≤ 50,000	12	10.00	96,417
50,001 – 100,000	36	30.00	
100,001 – 150,000	42	35.00	
> 150,000	30	25.00	
Access to credit facilities			
Yes	32	26.67	
No	88	73.33	
Access to extension agents			
Yes	39	32.50	
No	81	67.50	

Field Survey, 2025

Plantain processing activities and products available in the study area.

The result from Table 2 presented the plantain processing activities and products available in the study area. Farmers group was the major (56.67%) source of raw plantain in the study area, while some respondents (18.33%) utilized the plantain from previous planting season. Majority (70%) of the respondents employed hired labor. Also, for most respondents (54.16%), wholesalers are the major product off-takers. The majority (52.25%) of the respondents attested that roasted plantain was the most available product in the area, followed by flour (33.54%) and then chips (14.19%). It could be deduced that many processors engaged in roasted plantain business because of the less technology involved in processing it. Likewise, it is highly demanded for among the transporters as a fast and read-to-eat food (Nwosu *et al.*, 2016).

Table 2: Distribution of plantain processing activities and products available. (n = 120)

Plantain processing activities	Frequency
Percentage	
Source of raw plantain	
Farmers Group	68
56.67	
Cooperative Group	16
13.33	
Ministry of Agric	14
11.67	
Previous Planting Season	22
18.33	
Type of labour use	
Family Labor	36
30.00	
Hired Labor	84
70.00	
Major product off takers	
Wholesalers	65
54.16	
Retailers	41
34.17	
Companies/Industries	14
11.67	
Plantain products available*	
Chips	22
14.19	

Flour	52
33.54	
Roasted	81
52.25	

Field survey, 2025 *multiple response
Cost and return structure of plantain processing in the study area.

The result in table 3 reveals that on average, the total cost incurred on plantains was N265,350 per month. The total return and net return were N712,227 and N222,976.94 respectively. This result implies that plantain processing in the study area is profitable, and this should encourage more entrants into the business of plantain processing and marketing. This justifies one of the needs of this study as plantain offers many socioeconomic benefits including income provision. It can be deduced from the above result that plantain marketing is a profitable venture. The result of the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) further reiterated the profitability of plantain processing in the area. The BCR value of 1.46 implies that for every one naira expended on processed plantain ₦1.46k is realized. It means that the processor makes a gain of 46 kobo for each naira they invest in the business. This conforms with the findings of (Bamidele, 2021, Aina *et al.*, 2012, Oladejo *et al.*, 2011).

Dankyi *et al.*, (2007) also in his report revealed that farmers are aware of the various production technologies, however low farm-gate pricing with traders determining prices has been a major hindrance to production and marketing. It is therefore obvious that increased production without corresponding well developed and efficient marketing system will amount to wastage of resources (Adetunji and Adesina, 2008).

Table 3: Cost and return structure of plantain processors.

Items	Average Value (N)	% of Total
cost		
Total Revenue (TR)	712,227	
Variable cost		
Raw plantain	265,350	54.24
Labour	68,021.6	13.90
Transportation	72,314.8	14.78
Storage	25,960	5.31
Total Variable Cost (TVC)	431,646.4	
Depreciation cost on knife	22,584	4.61
Depreciation cost on bowl	29,650	6.06
Depreciation cost on sack	5,369.66	1.10
Total Fixed Cost (TFC)	57,603.66	
Total Cost (TC)	489,250.06	
Gross Margin (TR - TVC)	280,580.6	
Net Income	222,976.94	
BCR	1.46	

Field survey, 2024
Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, it can be concluded that the prospects of plantain processing are high. It is therefore a good business opportunity for creating employment for many Nigerians to become actors in the plantain value chain (as inputs dealers, farmers, marketers, transporters, and processors). It was concluded that roasted plantain is the most available plantain product in the area. The result of the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) further

reiterated the profitability of plantain processing in the area. The BCR value of 1.46 implies that for every one naira expended on processed plantain ₦1.46k is realized. It means that the processor makes a gain of 46 kobo for each naira they invest in the business. The study recommended that Government and relevant stakeholders should consider policy interventions that support the growth of plantain processing enterprises, including subsidies for processing equipment, tax incentives, and grants for small-scale entrepreneurs.

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